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Study of Ionospheric Variation Using COSMIC-RO During Solar Flare in October 2024-A Case Study

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ABSTRACT: Continuous monitoring and analysis of Ionosphere during different geophysical phenomena are crucial for advancing the understanding of solar-terrestrial interactions and their impacts on space-based technologies, improving the space weather prediction and mitigation strategies. For the first time ionospheric variation over Himalayan region during intense solar flare have been studied using COSMIC2 mission. The outcome of this study can lay the foundation on the work to investigate the extent of perturbation and hence the communication disruption being emanated by Solar Flare. The investigation focuses on essential ionospheric parameters, including NmF2, HmF2, and Total Electron Content (TECs), and provides an insightful examination of electron concentration in the E layer during seven X-class solar flare of different intensity occurred in October-2024. Both NmF2 and TECs are showing significant higher level of concentration during the two cycles of solar flare: 1-9th October 2024 and 24-31st October 2024 with notable higher HmF2. In E layer, peak electron concentration is decisively high with ETEC ranging 0.3 -1.2 TECU.

Keywords: Solar-Flare, Himalayan, NmF2, HmF2, COSMIC-RO

Introduction:

The extreme solar forcing on the Earth's ionosphere creates complex variations in the time-varying ionospheric current. One of the typical examples of extreme solar forcing is a solar flare event. A solar flare is a sudden heating of the solar atmosphere as a result of the violent release of the magnetic energy by magnetic reconnection, which is tightly tied to the dark spot areas on the surface of the Sun known as the sunspots [1]. Depending on the intensity of electromagnetic energy, solar flares are logarithmically categorized into A-, B-, C-, M-, and X-classes [2-4]. The peak flux of flares is split into linear scales between 1 and 9 except for X-class flares that have no upper limit. The classifications are based on X-ray brightness with wavelength 0.1–0.8 nm as measured by the Geostationary Operational Environmental Satellites 15 (GOES-15). The X-class flares are the most potent flares with the extra ionization that are capable of releasing large number of electron and ions into the interplanetary space thereby causing disturbances in the upper atmosphere [1, 5]. These disturbances, in turn, affect the Global Navigation Satellite System signals, shortwave radio communications [1, 6-8]. In addition to upper layers, when a solar flare erupts, the impact on the ionosphere in response to incident flare X-ray and EUV emission is known as sudden ionospheric disturbance (SID) [9] and affects various levels of the ionosphere depending on the incident wavelength, such as in the D (60-100Km) region [10], E layer [11-14] and occasionally in the F2 region also [5].

Solar flares emit far UV together with soft and hard X-rays that penetrate deeper in the atmosphere, temporarily ionizing the E region and D region. The ionization enhancement can

also perturb the geomagnetic field. These are often called a geomagnetic “crochet” or solar flare effect (sfe) [13, 15, 16, 17]. This leads to a substantial increase of the electron-density profile in the D-region which in turn changes the propagation conditions of radio waves that travel through it [2]. This has a particularly deleterious impact on HF radio waves that propagate through the D-region to reflect at higher altitude regions of the ionosphere.

Most of the previous works in general are concentrated to the TEC variation and none of them is conducted to the Himalayan region. Moreover, obtaining ionospheric information uninterruptedly at a fixed location using ground-based in-situ observation over this vast region of trough and crest for a specific duration of time is challenging and its maintenance is also costly, Space based LEO satellite data have been used to study the ionospheric variation during some of the most intense X -class solar flare occurred in 2024,

Materials and Methods:

Data and Method of Analysis

In 2024, the sun released over 50 X-class solar flares, and this year is also entitled to achieve the peak intensity of the 25th solar cycle. For the present study, a 57-day observational period starting from 19th-Sept-2024 to 14th-Nov-2024 has been considered, and in this interval, seven X-class solar flares of different intensities occurred on 1st, 3rd, 7th, 9th, 24th, 26th, and 31st October-2024. The details about the considered solar flare are taken from the website <https://www.spaceweatherlive.com>. To study the solar variability and geomagnetic variability during this observation period, the solar 10.7 cm flux F10.7 data and sum Kp index data have been taken from the World Data Centre website (<http://www.ukssdc.ac.uk>) of UKSSDC, UK, and from the websites (<http://wdc.kugi.kyoto-u.ac.jp>) of Kyoto, Japan, respectively, and for the ionosphere, the Constellation Observing System for Meteorology, Ionosphere, and Climate (COSMIC)/Formosa Satellite 2 COSMIC-2 mission observational data have been considered. This mission provides almost 4000-5000 Vertical Electron Density (VED) profiles per day throughout the globe. Detailed descriptions about this mission and its data format have been addressed on its official website (<http://www.cosmic.ucar.edu>). Like several previous studies [18-21], some realistic quality control criteria have been imposed to filter out suitable data sets for better quality and applicability of this study. A $10^{\circ} \times 10^{\circ}$ boxcar region in the great Himalayan region was chosen to accumulate the maximum number of vertical profiles, and finally, 406 vertical profiles have been sorted out to estimate the variation over this vulnerable region. Space-based LEO satellite data have been used to study the ionospheric variation during some of the most intense X-class solar flares that occurred in 2024.

Table 1. The date of solar flare along with its class and level occurred in October 2024. Taken from <https://www.spaceweatherlive.com/en/solar-activity>.

Date	Level	Time (UST)	Solar Flux
01.10.2024	X7.10	22.20	246
03.10.2024	X9.0	12.18	310
07.10.2024	X2.1	19.13	258
09.10.2024	X1.8 & X1.4	01.56 & 15.47	221
24.10.2024	X3.33	03.57	194
26.10.2024	X1.86	07.17	236
31.10.2024	X2.03	21.20	277

As the first step in the filtering process, profiles were selected based on the geographic latitude (GEO_LAT) and geographic longitude (GEO_LON) of HmF2, restricted to the coordinates 28N-38N and 72E-82E (see Fig. 1). Profiles that were unreadable, corrupted, or lacked the complete set of required information (i.e. missing NmF2 or negative densities etc) for further investigation were discarded. All the 406 VED profiles included in this study are in NetCDF format, from which information about ionospheric peak parameters, namely NmF2 and HmF2, can be easily extracted. The other two parameters, BTEC (1 TECU = 1E+16 el/m²) and TTEC (Bottom side and Topside integrated electron content), were calculated using specified equations (1).

$$(BTEC, TTEC) = \int_{(Balt, HmF2)}^{(HmF2, Talt)} Ne(z) dz \quad (1)$$

In the above equation (Eq. 1), Balt represents the Mean Sea Level Altitude (MSL_Alt) of the lowest point of the bottom side ionosphere, while Talt denotes the altitude of the highest point of the topside ionosphere.

Das Gupta et al. (2007) [22], in their groundbreaking research on ionospheric Ne content, indicated that the low-latitude ionosphere not only maintained maximum ionization but also exhibit significant temporal and spatial fluctuating TEC with high concentration. To curtail the effect of diurnal variability to the detected irregularity in the ionosphere, daily weighted mean [20] of each parameter has been calculated using equation (2). Each day was divided into four six-hour local time bins (0–6 LT, 6–12 LT, 12–18 LT, 18–24 LT) and thereafter, all the parameters (here P) associated with these four sub-intervals have been assigned the weights 4, 3, 2, and 1 (to mitigate the daytime extreme values assigning less weight to them), respectively with number of profiles N₄, N₃, N₂, N₁.

$$P(\text{ave}) = \frac{(4N_4P + 3N_3P + 2N_2P + N_1P)}{(4N_4 + 3N_3 + 2N_2 + N_1)} \quad (2)$$

Figure 1. The 10-degree square box study area in the Himalayan region

Result and Discussion:

Solar F10.7 and $\sum Kp$ index variation

In Figure 2, the solar flux and Kp index values have been plotted for the 57 days observational period covering the October-2024. Figure 2(a) i.e. the left panel indicates the solar flux values whereas the right one (i.e. Fig 2(b)) indicates the averaged Kp index. In each figure the red star indicates the day of X-class solar flare. Clearly the solar flux values achieve the peak with significant pattern of variation with Kp values are in normal range with diffusive nature of variability. The difference between two peaks of solar flux is nearly 28 days: one occurred on 3rd October 2024 and another on 31st, this fluctuation might be due to 27 days solar rotation [19-21]. Flux values are in the range of 145-310 sfu, whereas, Kp values are mostly less than 40 which exhibit the mild storm-level activity and no sudden rearrangement activity in the geomagnetic field observed.

Figure 2. Solar flux and Kp values during 57 days observation period starting from 19th - September 2024 to 14th November 2024

Variation in Peak Parameters

In Figure 3, the vertical distribution of weighted averaged electron density N_e in the range of 60-500KM have been plotted. In each of the panel the red colour star representing the days of the X-class solar flare. Clearly two separate regions of electron concentration, one near starting of October - 2024 and another in the last week of October - 2024. On the other hand, Figure 4 demonstrate concentration of peak parameters (NmF2 and HmF2) and two total electron content (TTEC and BTEC) throughout the observation period. The peak electron concentration, NmF2 (see Fig 4(a)) vary in between $5E+5$ (el/cm³) to $2.2E+6$ (el/cm³) in the high range 270-370km (Fig. 4(b)) with two separate and clear phase of variability. In case of first phase, NmF2 as well as TECs exhibit significant higher level of concentration whereas, in second phase these values showed lower low concentration which might be constrain to the intensity of the solar flare occurred in respective phase. Similarly, when concentration given to HmF2, it suggests that peak electron concentration (i.e. NmF2) placed mostly in the high-range of 290-370km which exhibit no clear pattern of variability as well as without any phase throughout the observation period. In maximum cases TEC exhibits higher level of concentration during the first series of solar flare whereas during the last phase this concentration little bit different though overall concentration in topside ionosphere is considerably higher, like BTEC varies between 5-20 (TECU) whereas in the top side part TTEC lies in the range 5-27 (TECU). It should be mentioned that, three X-class solar flare occurred in 2-3 days interval in each of the two phases of flare in October 2024.

Figure 3. Vertical distribution of electron concentration (N_e) during 57 days observational period starting from 19th -September 2024 to 14th November 2024.

Figure 4. Daily weighted averaged values of NmF2, HmF2, BTEC and TTEC during the 57-days observational period starting 19th September 2024 to 14th November 2024. The red colour star denotes the days of solar flare.

Variation in E layer

In Figure 5 E-layer electron concentration (NmE) as well as its electron content (E_{TEC}) have been displayed during the 57-days observational period starting from 19th September 2024 to 14th November 2024. The red colour stars in each panel denoting the days of occurring the X class solar flare in October 2024. In the left panel, Fig 5(a) the peak electron concentration NmE showing higher-high pattern of fluctuation during 1st October to 10th October in which period two most intense solar flare occurred: one on 1st October and another on 3rd October. Fact is that, these two flares are the most devastating flare with X9 and X7.1 happen in this month (see the table 1). Another series of flare occurred during the last week of October 2024, interestingly during this period NmE showing considerable stable lower level of concentration. Though the level of solar flare in this case is no so high as much as in previous case and difference in NmE concentration might be due the difference of intensity in solar flare. On the other hand, E_{TEC} showing steady lower level of concentration during both the case of series of solar flare, which is little bit direr from pattern of variability exhibited in case of NmE. But in case of flares occurred during last week of October 2024, E_{TEC} level getting lower-low concentration might be due to comparatively lower level of intensity of solar flare.

Figure 5. E-layer peak electron concentration (NmE) and total electron content (ETEC) during the 57 days observational period.

Conclusion:

To study the ionospheric variation due to the perturbation during seven strong solar flares occurred in October-2024 over the great Himalayan region, ionospheric variation has been analysed using 57 days observational period. Though, the magnitude of solar flare could be an option of doubt to the outcome of this study but it is clear that NmF2, BTEC and TTEC are showing prominent irregular variation during the two phases of X-class solar flares whereas HmF2 is little bit different. In case of E-layer peak electron concentration showing higher-high fluctuation during first phase of solar flares whereas in second phase it is opposite, might be due to lower intensity of flares occurred in this last phase. During solar flare events, the increased flux of X-rays and EUV radiation can dramatically increase ionization rates in the ionosphere, leading to enhanced electron densities. In summary, the study provided evidence that intense solar flares significantly perturb the ionosphere through enhanced ionization, heating, and compositional changes. Though the number of data profiles used here for the analysis may be an issue to the result and in future large number of profiles will be included in a details study in this regard.

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Conflict of interest

The author declare that he has no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

References

1. Tsurutani, B. T., Verkhoglyadova, O. P., Mannucci, A. J., Lakhina, G. S., Li, G., Zank, G. P., A brief review of “solar flare effects” on the ionosphere. *Radio Sci.* 44, (2009) 1–14. doi:10.1029/2008rs004029
2. Davies, K. *Ionospheric Radio*. London: Peter Peregrinus Limited. (1990), <https://doi.org/10.1049/PBEW031E>
3. Ishkov, V. *Catalog of Solar Flare Events With X-ray Class M1 - X > 17.5. XXIII Cycle of Solar Activity (1996–2008)* ESDB repository, GC RAS, Moscow, (2018), <https://doi.org/10.2205/ESDB-SAD-FE-02> (<http://www.wdcb.ru/stp/data/Solar%5FFlare%5FEvents/FI%5FXXIV.pdf>).
4. Oloketuyi, J., Liu, Y., & Zhao, M. The periodic and temporal behaviors of solar X-ray flares in solar cycles 23 and 24. *The Astrophysical Journal*, (2019), 874(1), 20. <https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/ab064c>
5. Scherliess L, Ionospheric Response to X-Ray and EUV Flux Changes During Solar Flares, *Geophysical Monograph Series*, (2016), ch18, <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118929216>.
6. Liu, J. Y., Lin, C. H., Chen, Y. I., Lin, Y. C., Fang, T. W., Chen, C. H., Solar flare signatures of the ionospheric GPS total electron content. *Journal of Geophysical Research*, (2006), III, A05308. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2005JA011306>
7. Berdermann, J., Kriegel, M., Banyś, D., Heymann, F., Hoque, M. M., Wilken, V., Ionospheric response to the X9.3 flare on 6 September 2017 and its implication for navigation services over Europe. *Space Weather*, (2018), 16, 1604–1615. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2018SW001933>
8. Buzás, A., Kouba, D., Mielich, J., Burešová, D., Mošna, Z., Koucká Knížová, P. and Barta, V., Investigating the effect of large solar flares on the ionosphere based on novel Digisonde data comparing three different methods. *Front. Astron. Space Sci.* (2023) 10:1201625. doi: 10.3389/fspas.2023.1201625
9. Saharan, S., Maurya, A., Dube A., Patil O. M., Singh, R., Sharma, M. Low latitude ionospheric TEC to the solar flares during the peak of solar cycle 24, *Adv. In Sci. Res.*, (2023), 72(9), 3890-3902. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asr.2023.07.015>
10. Ogunmodimu, O., Honary, F., Rogers, N., Falayi, E. O., & Bolaji, O. S. Solar flare induced cosmic noise absorption. *NRIAG Journal of Astronomy and Geophysics*, (2018), 7(1), 31–39. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nrjag.2018.03.002>
11. Curto, J. J., Amory-Mazaudier, C., Torta, J. M., & Menvielle, M. (1994). Solar flare effects at Ebre: Regular and reversed solar flare effects, statistical analysis (1953 to 1985), a global case study and a model of elliptical ionospheric currents. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Space Physics*, (1994), 99(A3), 3945. <https://doi.org/10.1029/93JA02270>
12. Curto, J. J., Marsal, S., Blanch, E., & Altadill, D. Analysis of the solar flare effects of 6 September 2017 in the ionosphere and in the Earth's magnetic field using spherical elementary current systems. *Space Weather*, (2018), 16, 1709–1720. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2018SW001927>
13. Rastogi, R. G., Pathan, B. M., Rao, D. R. K., Sastry, T. S., & Sastri, J. H. (1999). Solar flare effects on the geomagnetic elements during normal and counter electrojet periods. *Earth, Planets and Space*, (1999), 51(9), 947–957. <https://doi.org/10.1186/BF03351565>
14. Li, W., Yue, J., Yang, Y., He, C., Hu, A., & Zhang, K. Ionospheric and thermospheric responses to the recent strong solar flares on 06 September 2017. *Journal of*

- Geophysical Research: Space Physics*, (2018), 123, 8865–8883. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2018JA025700>
15. Qian, L., Wang, W., Burns, A. G., Chamberlin, P. C., Coster, A., Zhang, S.-R., & Solomon, S. C. Solar flare and geomagnetic storm effects on the thermosphere and ionosphere during 6–11 September 2017. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Space Physics*, (2019), 124, 2298–2311. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2018JA026175>
 16. Hamid, N. S. A., Halim, R. A. R., Sarudin, I., Yoshikawa, A. & Fujimoto, A., Examining Solar Flare Effects on Earth's Ionosphere using Ground-Based Measurements; *Sains Malaysiana*, (2023), 52(8) 2309-2322, <http://doi.org/10.17576/jsm-2023-5208-11>
 17. Fagundes, P. R., Pillat, V. G., Tardelli, A., Muella, M. T. A. H., 2024, Pole to Pole ionospheric disturbance due to Solar Flares during low solar activity, *Journal of Geophysical Research: Space Physics*, (2024) <https://doi.org/10.1029/2024JA032597>
 18. Aragon-Angel, A., Hernandez-Pajares, M., Juan, J.M., Sanz, J., Obtaining more accurate electron density profiles from bending angle with GPS occultation data: FORMOSAT-3/COSMIC constellation. *Adv. Space Res.* 43, 2009, 1694–1701. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.asr.2008.10.034>.
 19. Sripathi S, COSMIC observations of ionospheric density profiles over Indian region: Ionospheric conditions during extremely low solar activity period, *Indian J. of Radio & Space Phys.* 41 (2012) 98-109
 20. Mondal G, Gupta M, Sen G K; Variations in Electron Content Ratio and Semi-thickness Ratio during LSA and MSA periods and some Cyclone Genesis Periods using COSMIC satellite observations, *Adv. Space Res.* 54 (2014) 2151–2158, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.asr.2014.07.017>
 21. Mondal G, Gupta M & Sen G K, Climatology of the Ionosphere over low-latitude (Kolkata) using FORMOSAT-3/COSMIC satellite observation. *J. of Earth System Sci.*, 124(2015) 291-301, doi: 10.1007/s12040-015-0548-y
 22. Das Gupta A, Paul A & Das A, Ionospheric total electron content (TEC) studies with GPS in the equatorial region, *Indian J. Radio Space Phys.*, 36 (2007) 278–292.